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Introduction

Many people wonder what Tourette's syndrome is exactly. Although I sure people have seen from movies, would think someone with Tourette's would curse a lot loudly, or say inappropriate expressions, but that is less likely to occur. Tourette's syndrome is one of many disorders in a human. It is a neurological disorder that makes people lose control of their body, twitch uncontrollably, and shout out unusual words, also may cause blinking repeatedly, these are known as tics. This disorder is known to be hereditary, but also may just so happen due to stress and what not. It is known when having Tourette's syndrome; you may also have another sort of disorder. Sadly, there is no cure for this mysterious disorder, but with professional help and medication, the tics can be less severe.

Tourette's syndrome in the movie "Front of the Class"

The story revolves around a kid named, Brad Cohen . He had Tourette syndrome since he was a kid. At school, he would make a clamor, and the educator would think he did it purposefully to disturb the class. At the point when in lesser high, Cohen had poor associate relations. As a grown-up, Cohen needed a whole lot to be an instructor. Anyway no chairman would contract him. After much, much having a go at, voyaging all over creation, Cohen was at last procured as a second-grade instructor. Anyhow that was just a large portion of the fight. A few children made fun of him, and one guardian hauled her tyke out of his class in light of the fact that she needed a "typical" instructor for her kid. Cohen needed to set out the law. While neighborly with kids, he needed to demonstrate that he was a power figure, not a pal.

In time, Cohen more than surpassed desires. To start with the kids, and after that other people, adored him. The motion pictures viably gives the message that test of managing a handicap can be surpassed by the test of managing how others treat you in view of their impression of your incapacity, and the test of persuading grown-ups that your inability doesn't characterize you can be more troublesome than persuading offspring of the same.

"Front of the Class" may be one of the first to clarify the inquisitive trauma of Tourette syndrome. Obliviousness and disarray will dependably influence those with Tourettes, and additionally the individuals who experience such individuals. "Front of the Class" is the most penultimate film ever to uncover the torment of Tourettes, as well as to clarify the contrasts between the numerous shifting manifestations of this "disorder". The film is remarkable in its genuineness, trustworthiness and life-certifying message.

Tourette syndrome "In A Surgeon's Life"

Dr. Sacks, an extraordinary neurologist specializes in the exploration of mentally disordered people. He gets personal with these people engaging a relationship with them so that he can explore not just the neurological disease but also the person. In this account he interacts with Dr. Carl Bennett who is a victim of Tourette syndrome. Bennett has Tourette's, the condition the causes severe tics and the calling out of socially inappropriate phrases. These symptoms are stronger or weaker depending on context, and the amazing fact is that Bennett is an accomplished surgeon and pilot.

Tourette's syndrome has the misnomer of being a disease where you use profanity and yell inappropriate words in a public environment. However, it can be much more serious and challenging to deal with that is only a symptom of the disease. The disorder was first documented in 1885 by a French Doctor named Georges Gilles de la Tourette; he would be considering a Neurologist in today standards. The Doctor Georges Gilles de la Tourette Name the disorder "maladie des tics" and he diagnosed nine patients in 1885 with the disorder who all demonstrated the normal symptoms of Turrets. The symptoms can have a vast array of different characteristics and can be different for each person. It involves unusual repetitive movements or unwanted sounds that can't be controlled, these are categorized as tics. The disorder was later renamed in his honor by Jean-Martin Charcot, the director at the hospital (Sacks, 1995).

The writing "A Surgeon's Life" is about Tourette's syndrome. The disease is also known for the use of inappropriate word such as profanity at inappropriate places, this is known as Coprolalia, and repeating the words or phrases of others similar to a parrot is called echolalia. Coprolalia is a very challenging part of the disorder for patients suffering with it and is an involuntary action that the patient has no control over. There is a misconception that this is what Tourette's is however this is just a possible symptom of the disorder. This actually happens in

less than ten to fifteen percent of people suffering from Tourette. This misconception was created by the movies and television. An example of this is in Deuce Bigalow, where Amy Poehler plays a woman stricken with a severe case of Turrets. This disorder makes a much bigger impact on the lives of the people than what was demonstrated in this movie. They can have the issue of how to deal with the public with the disorder and the challenges of dealing with everyday life. Furthermore, there can be other complications such as anger control issue which can stem from dealing with this disorder and asking the question why me. ADHD, Attention Deficit Hyperactive Disorder, is also very closely connected to the disorder and OCD, Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder. The patient can also suffer from impulsive behavior and poor social skills (Sacks, 1995).

The international prevalence, epidemiology, and clinical phenomenology of Tourette syndrome: A cross-cultural perspective

An estimated 2% of the population has Tourette syndrome and this disability was added to IDEA in 2004. This syndrome falls under the category listed in IDEA as and other health impairment. Most people mistake Tourette syndrome as a behavioral or emotional condition when actually it is a neurological condition. Students that have Tourette syndrome will not automatically be eligible for related services or special education. There are factors that are looked at, evaluations to be studied, and it depends on whether having Tourette syndrome negatively affects school performance (Robertson, Eapen & Cavanna, 2009).

Tourette syndrome is a neurobiological disorder characterized by tics (involuntary, rapid, sudden movements) and/or vocal outbursts that occur repeatedly. This syndrome is also inherited and first identified in childhood normally from ages 7 through 10. Tourette syndrome is

four times as likely to be diagnosed in boys as in girls. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, poor impulse control, behavioral outbursts, and obsessive compulsive disorder also can co-occur with the syndrome, which further complicates the lives of those affected (Robertson et.al, 2009).

The best way to help students that have Tourette syndrome is to have an individualized action plan for the student to help reduce tics, reduce the consequences that come with having the tics, and help get rid of the other symptoms of Tourette syndrome. There is not one specific way to help the student with Tourette because there are different needs to be addressed for every individual, but there are a few general strategies that should help the students with Tourette syndrome to be as successful as they can (Kutscher & Attwood, 2014).

A student with Tourette syndrome need released free time. It is nearly impossible for students to stop the tics almost as hard as it is to hold in a sneeze. We do not want our students to sit in class all day only focusing on keeping the tics from coming out. A way to help these students is to give them a time where they can go privately to let the tics happen. This strategy will help the student be able get away from their peers to avoid embarrassment. (Shaw et. al, 2007) These students can also use these safe places to go between activities to be able to regroup and calm down, which may reduce the possibly of tics (Robertson et.al, 2009).

Conclusion

People with Tourette's are harmless; they are just regular people with some troubles. Patients with this disorder are individuals just like people without any disorder. They feel the need to hide, or be embarrassed for having these tics. I feel they should shine just as much as a person without it would, although they are different, having Tourette's patients should feel dumb or embarrassed. It is not their fault they have this problem and people should understand.it is best

to comfort a patient diagnosed with this disorder so they do not feel out of place or different from the rest. Let the person express what they might have to say or do (Villa, Thousand & Nevin, 2008). Like stated before Tourette's is not some weird disease that cause people to shout out bad words, or do some inappropriate movement. Nor is it contagious, and not yet has a cure, but somewhere down the line, someone will hopefully come up with a cure to get rid of Tourette's.

References

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